

Psychological Capital: The Key To Success In Professional Life And Personal Development

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Abstract

In this article, in the light of the study data conducted to reveal the effects of psychological capital, flow experience and emotion management on job satisfaction and work-life balance, the effect of human psychological capital, which is the main role of working life, on job satisfaction and personal development was touched upon, and the importance of psychological capital, which has taken its place in literature and research, especially in working life, was emphasized once again.

Keywords: *Psychological Capital, Business Life, Personal Development*

Introduction

Due to the developments from past to present, we are currently experiencing a transition from agriculture to industry, from industry to the service sector, and from the service sector to the information age. When we look at work life, which dominates a large part of human life, from a historical perspective, it becomes evident that financial capital was prioritized in the 19th century, technological capital in the 20th century, and human capital has gained prominence in the 21st century. In this information age, it is clear that human capital is the most crucial element of working life, and no technology can replace it.

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Traditional Economic Capital	What Do I Have ?	Financing Tangible Assets
Human Capital	What Do I Know?	Experience Education Talent Information Opinions
Social Capital	Who do I know?	Relationships Friends Connection Network
Psychological Capital	Who am I?	Self-Efficacy <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Hope➤ Optimism➤ Flexibility

Figure 1: Types of Capital (Luthans, 2004)

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As mentioned above, the view that capital is the primary resource in the global world has gradually lost its validity, giving way to the human factor. This shift has underscored the importance of prioritizing employees in organizational productivity and efficiency.

In its early stages, psychology focused on the negative, darker aspects of human behavior, such as illnesses, failures, helplessness, burnout, and hopelessness. However, in light of contemporary studies, psychology has evolved and now prioritizes issues such as individual well-being, potential, and the pursuit of a fulfilling life (Keleş, 2011, p. 345).

Economic Capital

Bourdieu defines the concept of economic capital as the relationship between a person's possessions, property, and income, while Marx refers to it as the capitalist class that controls the means of production (Bourdieu 1986, Swartz 1997).

Human Capital

Although human capital is often defined as an individual's accumulation of knowledge, a more comprehensive explanation emphasizes that it is not static but constantly evolving. It refers to the skilled labor force that enables the positive development of knowledge and plays a crucial role in the positive progression of the economic and social welfare levels of nations within an economy (Şimşek & Kadılar, 2010).

Social Capital

Bourdieu defines social capital as the total of actual and potential resources linked to possessing durable networks of relationships (Erselcan, 2009). Similarly, Field emphasizes that

the networks of relationships, which connect and nourish one another, are the lifeblood of social capital (Ekinci et al., 2011).

Psychological Capital

Psychological capital is described by Goldsmith as "personality traits that emphasize individual productivity in psychology, encompassing individuals' views of themselves, their attitudes towards work, ethical compliance, as well as their overall approaches to life" (Goldsmith et al., 1999).

Another definition of psychological capital refers to it as a concept that involves the positive development and enhancement of attitudes and behaviors observable throughout the organization (Temiz, 2016).

A more comprehensive definition by Luthans explains psychological capital as the individual's confidence to take on and put in the necessary effort to succeed at challenging tasks, their belief in their success both in the present and future, their ability to find ways to achieve their goals, and their resilience in the face of difficulties, while maintaining this strength sustainably (Luthans, 2012). Furthermore, compared to other forms of capital, its capacity to change and develop through desire, experience, and education makes it both notable and promising.

Dimensions of Psychological Capital

When examining the sub-dimensions of Psychological Capital, four key concepts emerge: self-efficacy, which refers to an individual's belief in their own abilities and capacity to cope with challenges; hope, which represents the motivation to act and the belief in a positive future; optimism, which involves the expectation of success and the belief that good things will

happen; and emotional resilience, defined as the strength to endure difficulties, adaptability, flexibility, and responses to change (Gooty et al., 2009).

Luthans and colleagues (2007), who have contributed significantly to the field of positive psychology, addressed these four fundamental dimensions—self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience—when measuring psychological capital. They further analyzed these dimensions within the context of work and organizations, thereby introducing a new conceptual framework (Gohel, 2012).

Self-Efficacy (Confidence)

One of the sub-dimensions of psychological capital, self-efficacy, is defined by Gardner and Pierce (1998) as an individual's belief in their ability to successfully manage a task and achieve the desired outcome.

Bandura (1997) approached the concept more comprehensively by including notions such as task mastery, vicarious learning and role modeling, social persuasion, and psychological or physiological arousal. He later defined self-efficacy as the belief in one's own abilities, as well as the planning of all necessary behaviors to achieve personal goals (Avey et al., 2006).

Another definition of the concept highlights that employees strive to successfully complete difficult tasks when faced with challenges in order to achieve success (Eid et al., 2012).

Based on the above definitions, self-efficacy can be explained as an individual's belief in their capacity to activate the necessary actions, cognitive processes, and motivation to successfully complete a specific task.

Hope

A second dimension of Psychological Capital, hope, was described by Jerome Frank (1968) as an attribute that fosters a person's well-being and serves as a catalyst for action.

According to Miller (1985), hope is a concept that protects an individual from potential negative influences from the external environment, enabling the person to realize their potential. It encompasses the individual's expectations, emotions, and desires for the future (Akman & Korkut, 1993).

Another definition of hope was provided by Snyder, who described it as the sum of perceived capacities to generate pathways toward desired goals and the perceived motivation to use those pathways. Subsequently, Snyder's hope theory outlined three interrelated components: thinking about goals, thinking about pathways and methods, and agency thinking (Snyder et al., 1991).

Optimism

Optimism, as a dimension of psychological capital, is defined in the Turkish Language Institution (TDK) dictionary as a "personal trait or attitude oriented towards evaluating every thought and action as good" (Demiray, 1994).

In the context of positive psychology and psychological capital studies, optimism has been frequently discussed by Seligman and Schulman (1986), who describe it as the internal state of an individual related to achieving success in various domains, demonstrating willpower to maintain continuous success, and the internal condition concerning the attainment of success (Avey et al., 2006). Optimism involves the belief that good things will happen in the future, alongside the likelihood of attributing experienced events to certain causes (Akçay, 2011).

Additionally, Özkalp (2009) describes optimism as a motivating force representing health, determination, and success at various stages of life. It encompasses the awareness of one's

state, the ability to cope with stress, control stressors, and devise strategies in response to any encountered adversity (Aspinwall & Tedeschi, 2010).

Despite these definitions, Kutanis and Oruç (2014) highlight that optimism, as one of the significant sub-dimensions of psychological capital, is noted as one of the most debated but least understood concepts.

Reviewing research on optimism, a notable study observed 941 Dutch individuals aged 65-85 throughout a year. The data revealed that 57% of individuals with the lowest levels of optimism had died, whereas only 30% of those with the highest levels of optimism had passed away (Giltay et al., 2004, 2007).

Another significant study by Finnish researchers followed 2,482 male participants over nearly a decade. It was found that those with a pessimistic outlook had a much higher mortality rate compared to optimists. This research demonstrated that a positive outlook is influential not only for psychological well-being but also for biological health.

From an organizational perspective, optimism reflects the positive implications of employees' preferences and thoughts that contribute to their success both now and in the future (Eid et al., 2012). Employees with this trait are noted to exhibit a greater tendency to work, be more determined and successful in achieving their goals and expectations, feel less inadequate, and perceive themselves as more active both mentally and physically compared to others (Şen et al., 2017).

Psychological Resilience

The concept of psychological resilience, which is one of the dimensions of psychological capital, is defined by Hunter (2001) as the process of adapting and achieving success. Another interpretation of this concept is provided by Luthans et al. (2007), who describe it as the effort and striving shown to overcome various negative situations, such as obstacles and uncertainty.

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Another notable definition is that psychological resilience refers to the ability of individuals to respond differently to unexpected situations and to offer alternatives (Rodriguez & Carvajal et al., 2010).

From the perspective of organizational behavior, psychological resilience is the capacity to maintain oneself in the face of unexpected potential situations, encountered obstacles, failures, conflicts, and the increasing sense of responsibility and challenges (Polatçı et al., 2017).

What distinguishes the dimension of psychological resilience from the other dimensions of psychological capital, such as self-efficacy, optimism, and hope, is its incorporation of both reactive and proactive approaches.

- Reactive: This approach involves responding to events as they unfold when faced with a situation.
- Proactive: This approach involves anticipating and addressing potential future problems, contributing significantly to personal and professional development (Luthans et al., 2007).

Job Satisfaction

The concept of job satisfaction was initially defined as "working in a factory with the least amount of stress and fatigue" (Taylor & Gilbert, 1911). The concept later emerged through scientific studies known as the Hawthorne Studies conducted by Elton Mayo and his colleagues in the 1920s at the Western Electric Company. The Hawthorne Studies drew attention to the impact of worker attitudes on performance and productivity, leading to the definition that "a happy worker is a productive worker."

Another definition of job satisfaction is described as the total of an individual's positive perceptions toward their job (Locke, 1976; Oshagbemi, 1999).

The Role of Psychological Capital in the Workplace

Psychological capital is dynamic and open to development. In this regard, psychological capital significantly influences and supports the sustainability of the increasingly globalized work environment, leading to improved performance in a noticeable and positive way.

Looking at the benefits of positive psychological capital to organizations, it enhances employees' mental well-being, increases success and job satisfaction, fosters employee engagement, contributes to improved organizational commitment, creates and positively impacts organizational climate, facilitates organizational change, and reduces absenteeism. As outlined above, positive psychological capital is an indispensable element for both employees and organizations (Zağlı, 2016).

Psychological capital contributes to employees' desire to produce, take responsibility, maintain positive feelings towards work, and nurture a sense of belonging. Understanding and developing the positive aspects of employees thus adds significant value to organizational structure (Sarıcı, 2015).

In summary, psychological capital is a force that increases the likelihood of success derived from an employee's determination and motivation (Luthans, 2012). A study conducted by Salam in 2017 on 104 faculty members at universities in Thailand found a positive relationship between job satisfaction and psychological capital, with a notable negative relationship between job satisfaction and the dimensions of psychological capital.

Recent studies suggest that individuals experiencing a stressful work environment and high work-family conflict exhibit significantly lower levels of psychological capital compared to less stressed individuals (Newman et al., 2014). Additionally, current research indicates that high levels of uncertainty in organizations lead to lower levels of psychological capital, which in turn triggers higher stress levels (Epitropaki, 2013).

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Overall, research findings suggest that employees who efficiently utilize their personal resources exhibit higher job engagement. There is a notable relationship between psychological capital and job engagement, with psychological capital's dimensions—self-efficacy, hope, resilience, and optimism—contributing significantly to job engagement (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008; Luthans et al., 2008).

In conclusion, research has generally recognized that psychological capital positively and significantly affects job performance, motivation, and job satisfaction. Based on these findings, businesses should develop and implement strategies to support these internal resources, which can contribute to employees' personal development and enhance organizational success (Çetin & Varoğlu, 2015). Higher levels of psychological capital enable employees to derive greater satisfaction from their work, while job satisfaction positively contributes to the development of employees' psychological capital. This meaningful and positive relationship between psychological capital and job satisfaction highlights their importance as key factors in enhancing both individual and organizational performance.

Objective

This research aims to examine psychological capital as an independent variable, which encompasses an individual's self-confidence, ability to exert effort in challenging tasks, finding ways to achieve goals, confidence in success, resilience in the face of unexpected problems, and the ability to maintain these qualities. Job satisfaction and work-life balance, which can be described as the material rewards obtained from one's job and the pleasure and satisfaction derived from it, as well as the balance between work and family roles and responsibilities that contributes to overall well-being, are considered dependent variables.

The study focuses on court employees, who face higher levels of workload, job stress, physical and psychological fatigue compared to other institutions, and are required to interact continuously with citizens, superiors, and colleagues. The results of this research aim to raise

awareness among institutional employees regarding both their professional and personal lives and to provide insights for institutional managers to recognize current conditions and seek solutions for improvement. It is anticipated that this research will serve as a starting point for future theoretical studies.

Methodology

In this study, employees under hierarchical supervision, who are of primary importance in organizational operations, were selected as research participants. The target population of the study consists of personnel working in the Ankara Courthouse. It was learned from the relevant departments of this institution that approximately 3,350 individuals were employed as of 2024. The prepared survey form was distributed to Directors, Court Clerks, Officers, Service Staff, and Bailiffs working in the court and prosecutor's office departments of the courthouse. Considering the size of the population, a total of 418 individuals were included in the study.

The data obtained from the survey forms were processed using the SPSS 26.0 software. Parametric tests, specifically the T-test for comparisons between two groups, were applied to the data for demographic variables including gender, age, number of children, marital status, education level, years of service, and job title.

Findings

According to the correlation analysis conducted to examine the relationships between the scales and sub-dimensions used in the study, there are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) and positive relationships ($r = 0.609$) between work-life balance and job satisfaction. As scores for work-life balance increase, job satisfaction will also increase.

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Figure 2: Descriptive Statistics for Research Scales

There are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) and positive relationships ($r = 0.403$) between psychological capital and job satisfaction. As scores for psychological capital increase, job satisfaction will also increase. Additionally, there are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) and positive relationships ($r = 0.519$) between psychological capital and work-life balance. As scores for psychological capital increase, scores for work-life balance will also increase.

Figure 3: Relationships (correlation) between the scales used in the research

In summary, the results of this research indicate that there is a significant and positive relationship between psychological capital, job satisfaction, and work-life balance.

Results

In the research covered in the article, it is evident that judicial employees, who were included as participants, are engaged in significant struggles due to their societal positions, the nature of their work, and the negative factors experienced in contemporary settings. Based on the literature and research findings, some key results are outlined below:

- If employees work in fields that require continuous close interaction with others, their feelings of anxiety are likely to increase (Baltaş & Baltaş, 1993).
- In professions that involve constant face-to-face contact with the public, the communication and interaction with people, and the resulting emotional intensity, will affect individuals' inner worlds as well (Ergin, 1992, p. 145).
- An employee who holds a negative attitude toward their profession and current living conditions is likely to face numerous psychological and physical barriers (Maslach & Leiter, 1997).
- While the happiness derived from one's job positively influences all areas of life, any experienced negativities will adversely affect other areas of life, leading to unhappiness and reluctance (Sevimli & Işcan, 2005).

In many studies that identify a positive relationship between job satisfaction and work-life balance, the following components are essential for developing psychological capital: positive thinking, self-confidence, emotional awareness, social support, collaboration and support at work, goal-setting, physical and mental health through exercise, healthy sleep, balanced

nutrition, self-care, positive relationships, hobbies, and artistic activities. It is also important to define boundaries between work and personal life and to address time management.

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